

Nursery Management for Wild Asparagus Propagation

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The agronomic knowledge on wild asparagus (*Asparagus acutifolius* L.) cultivation is currently enough to foster its introduction in the farming plans of marginal areas. However, a major constraint for implementing local value chains is the scarcity of propagation material. Local nurseries should fix this flaw in collaboration with farmers willing to test wild asparagus either in agroforestry or pure stand systems.

In the past, the cultivation of nursery material was limited by the dormancy of the asparagus seeds. Such dormancy is of physiological nature (non-deep physiological dormancy) and is affected by genetic and environmental factors. For instance, wild asparagus ecotypes belonging to areas with mild conditions could generate seeds with low levels of dormancy; as well, the occurrence of a mild vegetative season could lead to produce a large proportion of non-dormant seeds in ecotypes from xeric areas. At present, the scarce germinability of the wild asparagus seeds has been overcome through a number of techniques. The seed stratification, although time demanding, is one of the most reliable and easy to apply for the nursery. Firstly, the seeds should be picked up from spontaneous plants in the area of cultivation, so that the used germplasm will reflect the local genetic variability and, likely, the best adaptability to the local cultivation environment. The seeds should then be stratified in sand in a place protected by the weathering and maintained in humid conditions till the next autumn for germination in the following spring. In order to shorten the nursery operations, further experimental evidence indicate that a 56 day long warm stratification (23°C) can reduce the time span for the dormancy interruption, allowing to obtain a regular germination directly in the following spring.

Two years old asparagus seedlings should be used for transplanting in the final stand.

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